

YASHIL

№10

Iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnik, ilmiy-ommabop jurnal

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7491

ISSN: 2992-8982

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
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- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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Elektron nashr. 983 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 1-oktabrdan ruxsat etildi.

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Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

««Yashil» iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot» jurnali
O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi
Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUASSIS: «Ma'rifat-print-media» MChJ

HAMKORLARIMIZ: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

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FORMS AND MODELS OF FAMILY ECONOMY

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Toshkent iqtisodiyot va texnologiyalar universiteti
Iqtisodiy fanlar kafedrasida katta o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya. Maqoladagi mazmun oilaning ichki iqtisodiy tuzilmasi va budjetni shakllantirish jarayoniga qaratilgan bo'lib, unda oila a'zolari o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy munosabatlar aniq tizimga asoslanganligi ko'rsatilgan. Oilaning umumiy budjetidan foydalanish va qarorlar qabul qilishda har bir a'zo moliyaviy jihatdan mustaqil harakat qila olmasligi, shuningdek, har bir qaror butun oila farovonligiga ta'sir ko'rsatishi bilan bog'liq. Shu nuqtayi nazardan, maqolada oilaviy iqtisodiyotda iqtisodiy qarorlarning oqibatlari va o'zaro bog'liqliklar chuqur tahlil etilishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: oila iqtisodiyotini yuritishning shakllari va modellari, shaxsiy moliya, oila budjetidagi mablag'lar, shaxslarning iqtisodiy xatti-harakatlari.

Аннотация. Рассматриваются модели ведения семейной экономики, которая имеет свою внутреннюю структуру и сложившуюся систему экономических отношений, возникающих между её членами при формировании и использовании общего бюджета. Члены семьи, проживающие в её составе, не могут быть полностью финансово независимыми и должны учитывать последствия своих экономических решений, влияющих на формирование благополучия семьи.

Ключевые слова: формы и модели ведения семейной экономики, личные финансы, фонды в бюджете семьи, экономическое поведение индивидов.

Abstract. The article examines models of family economics, which feature their own internal structure and an established system of economic relations arising between members during the formation and use of a common budget. Family members living within this structure cannot be entirely financially independent and must consider the consequences of their economic decisions, which affect the overall well-being of the family.

Key words: forms and models of family economics, personal finances, funds in the family budget, economic behavior of individuals.

INTRODUCTION

The family is the fundamental unit of society and is protected by both society and the state [1, p.12]. Therefore, our government places special emphasis on ensuring the material and moral integrity of families. According to recent data, there are more than 8.3 million families in our country, with over 2 million classified as young families. To enhance youth policy, a comprehensive system of measures is being implemented to support young families both morally and materially, providing them with decent housing and improved social and living conditions [2, p.15].

The economic behavior of individuals within market relations emphasizes that their decisions are driven by personal interests, which primarily benefit themselves. In this context, personal finances play a central role, coordinating economic decisions made both within and outside the family.

An individual's level of well-being and quality of life are closely linked to the structure and management of family (household) finances—the environment where personal development begins, life experience is gained, and the foundations of financial management are established. The family, as the starting point for financial, property, and consumer relationships, significantly influences a person's daily behavior and financial decision-making once they become independent.

The relationships within a family differ from those outside of it, as they are often based on kinship. Within the household, family members typically do not pay one another for maintaining the home, keeping order, raising children, or caring for elderly relatives. Financial exchanges, such as pocket money, are not payments for services rendered but rather support within the family structure.

However, a household is not a homogeneous entity, as it reflects both the individual interests of its members and the collective interests of the family as a whole. There are numerous aspects of managing family finances that people often overlook. The primary concern in modern society is the fear of losing financial independence — a concern tied not only to financial security but also to the capacity for wise financial management. For an individual to advance to a higher social level, a more sophisticated approach to personal finances is required. A financially secure person will seek to create a different social environment in which they feel more comfortable than they would at a lower social level.

Cultural ideals and values related to the integration of men and women in both the family and labor market vary across societies. These ideals are closely linked to cultural norms concerning intergenerational relationships and responsibilities within the family [3, p.79].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The model of managing family finances and the relationships that develop within the household play a crucial role in shaping the family's economic status. This depends on the financial literacy and behavior of all its members, how and by whom decisions are made regarding the distribution of funds, and the roles assigned to each spouse in the process. Effective management and a clear understanding of how to allocate surplus financial resources can provide a fresh perspective on the family budget, enabling the optimal flow of funds both within the household and beyond.

Family financial policy may be influenced by either traditional or emerging modern models of financial management, which are often shaped by various approaches to household budgeting and constrained by the economic relations of the social groups that make up the household.

Household decision-making models encompass not only broad, national perspectives that allow for the evaluation of resource flows and economic development indicators, but also an analysis of internal dynamics, assessing the household's varying degrees of autonomy from the dominant economy [4, p.31].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research on the typology of family financial management models has identified a wide range of approaches and management forms, ranging from a common budget that consolidates the financial resources of all family members to independent budgets managed by each individual member.

The financial relationships within the household, including the control of incoming funds, their distribution, and redistribution, vary depending on the level of control over the family budget and the influence each member has on its formation.

While the common interests of all family members may serve as the basis for the family's economic status, the formation of financial behavior is highly individual and may not apply uniformly to everyone.

Currently, the household budget is calculated as the balance of assets and liabilities of all family members contributing their financial resources to the common fund. When evaluating the elements of the household budget, it is important to consider the distribution of decision-making power within the family, access to both shared and individual financial resources, and the specific financial behaviors of the household members.

This variation arises because the methods of managing household finances differ significantly, and money within a family is not impersonal; it typically belongs to the family member who serves as the primary earner, and ownership of the money generally remains unchanged.

When discussing the family budget, it is more accurate to refer to a «budget system» within a unified family budget, as each family member tends to maintain individual records of their income and expenditures, regardless of the household's financial management style (i.e., different types of individual funds).

In analyzing models of collective decision-making within households, especially concerning budget distribution, it is important to consider the personal behavior, contributions, and opinions of each family member, rather than relying solely on the concept of family consensus.

This is because the motivations behind personal finances may not always align with the household's collective goals, particularly when it comes to the unpaid responsibilities of running a shared household. Although one might wish to view the household as a homogeneous structure, the personal interests of the family member whose contribution to the budget is the largest will often dominate.

Matlin notes that economic interests related to property relations are the most straightforward. In practice, these manifest as needs for material goods and services. It is not just personal gain but the desire to maximize the satisfaction of needs that truly reflects human nature [5, p. 61].

At the same time, the family budget alone cannot fully characterize the household as a whole, as it only reflects the external material aspects of life (e.g., family composition, housing conditions, income, and expenses). However, in practice, it remains the primary way to describe the economic conditions of family life.

The family budget consolidates the income of all family members, used for both shared and personal purposes. Some researchers suggest that decision-making regarding the distribution of the family budget results from combining various preferences and focuses on how these preferences are balanced and implemented.

- based on consensus;
- in the manner adopted in cooperatives;
- market equilibrium within the household, etc. [6, P. 5, 6]; [5, P. 9].

There are «Unitary» and «Collective» models of decision-making processes in the household. Unitary models consider the household as a single entity that makes a coordinated decision and offers various mechanisms for distributing wealth and managing its budget. They assume the existence of an initial welfare function that forces all resources to be pooled, including labor, food, and other goods.

Kalabikhina believes that when analyzing micro-level decisions, it is necessary to consider the personal, not the family level. Such a need, in addition to ethical considerations about the right of the individual to independent development, is also dictated by modern trends that are changing the structure of the family and the distribution of labor between household members. Family decisions are not always the result of the voluntary consent of household members; they often represent the implementation of the will of the family member who has the greatest power in the family [4, P. 33].

The main criterion here is financial independence. Family members living in it are not completely free and must take into account the impact of the consequences of their economic decisions on others. The family usually agrees to make many decisions collectively, and its members must have the right to vote in the distribution of household responsibilities when it is determined who and in what form takes part in ensuring the life of the household.

According to S. Zagorodnikov, various funds can be formed as part of the household budget:

- individual, intended for individual family members and used to purchase various goods;
- joint, intended for the purchase of goods for general use;
- accumulation and provision fund (reserve fund), used for future capital expenditures or the formation of initial capital for commercial activities [8, P. 221].

All these differences, however, are of little significance in a macroeconomic context. Collective models of decision-making regarding the distribution of the family budget are classified

as either «Cooperative» or «Non-cooperative.» In cooperative models, the family (or household) is viewed as a cooperative enterprise, and decision-making is framed as an optimization problem aimed at maximizing the benefits of marriage for both partners, with the total income of the spouses as the primary constraint [9, pp. 99–119; 10, pp. 1299–1302]. At the same time, R. Pollack notes that economists have thus far worked with three primary models to describe resource and income distribution within families. These include Samuelson's family consensus model, Becker's altruistic model, and modern negotiation models. Although these models primarily focus on the relationship between husband and wife, they also provide a foundation for analyzing the dynamics between parents and children [11, p. 61].

The formation of financial relationships within the household raises many questions, particularly regarding the involvement of all members in contributing to the family's financial well-being. For example, in forming the income portion of the family budget, several «pitfalls» may arise: Should a spouse with a higher income contribute it fully to the common budget, or is it acceptable to retain a portion for personal expenses? In the case of unexpected income, should it be disclosed to the rest of the family?

Similarly, the formation of the expenditure portion of the family budget presents challenges. Who will be responsible for distributing the money? If the family chooses a joint budget model, will one person manage it, or will each member have the right to control a portion of the funds based on their contributions? Who will decide how much to allocate for food—the wife, traditionally seen as the «keeper of the hearth,» or the husband, if he is the primary breadwinner?

Indeed, a family's financial situation and standard of living are most clearly reflected in its budget, which is heavily influenced by both its economic behavior, particularly in terms of consumption, and the behavior of individual family members. Even in households with a single primary earner, the household budget is typically redistributed among all members.

One notable model of intra-family resource distribution is Becker's altruistic model, which differs from Samuelson's in its focus on internal family processes. This model assumes the presence of an «Altruist» within the family—someone whose preferences reflect concern for the well-being of all other members. The altruist's presence encourages the self-interested but rational behavior of family members to align with altruistic principles. As a result, resource distribution within the family is organized to maximize the altruist's utility function, taking into account the family's resource constraints [11, p. 62].

Pfau-Effinger identifies five gender-based models of family economies, each with several sub-variants: the model of the family economy; the model of the man as breadwinner and the woman as housewife; the model of the man as breadwinner and the woman as a partial housewife; the model of dual breadwinners with state childcare; and the model of dual breadwinners and dual housewives. Additionally, R. Crompton highlights the British model of two breadwinners with hired childcare [3, p. 80].

These models demonstrate how long-established economic relationships within families are being rethought, with traditional stereotypes, patriarchal norms, and perceptions of the main breadwinner's role evolving. Social systems perpetuate ideologies such as the belief that women should manage the household while men should work outside the home. Money, too, may be assigned specific uses: some may be designated for the husband (or wife) to spend on personal needs, while other portions are allocated for household expenses, such as food.

The primary breadwinners in the family often wield greater authority in decision-making, a pattern that extends to both spouses and children. Those who earn more also tend to do less housework. In return for their support, elderly parents may provide help, such as caring for children, which challenges the notion that rewards must always be of equivalent value [14, p. 342].

The question of which family member is responsible for the well-being of their loved ones and securing the family's future is complex. It could be the main breadwinner, who provides the

expanding fixed capital and driving technological progress. This, in turn, contributes to financing the overall economic growth of the state.

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“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz :Toshkent shahar,
Mirzo Ulug‘bek tumani Kumushkon ko‘chasi, 26-uy.

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>